

INFLUENCE OF EDUCATIONAL THOUGHT ON SOCIAL & RELIGIOUS LIFE BY JIDDU KRISHNAMURTI

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ABSTRACT:

The lessons of Krishnamurti don't have an everyday schedule, except, as people with propensities to sort and coordinate, attracted to contrasting him and Jean Paul Sartre, the dad of present day existentialism. Krishnamurti's works likewise remember the space of a human for the social and political situation. In the topic, "*Influence of Educational Thought on Social & Religious Life By Jiddu Krishnamurti*" states so very well that one can't know about something except if the other is likewise present. He gives the case of peacefulness: one can't know about peacefulness except if you understand what savagery is. Life itself is a development of connections, and we attempt to control and control it even in the most widely recognized occasions of life. For instance, when somebody lauds us, we fill in pride, when somebody affronts us we have rage filled in us; and what we do is act in manners that increment positive responses and decline negative remarks; the fact being that we are just carrying on with a half mechanized life, and accomplishing something constantly. Once more he underlines that all out mindfulness, and constant mindfulness, will prompt carrying on with a non-routine life, and no measure of discipline will make it happen - and, discipline isn't independence from the known.

KEYWORDS:

SOCIAL LIFE, JIDDU KRISHNAMURTI, RELIGIOUS LIFE, EDUCATIONAL THOUGHT, KNOWLEDGE.

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INTRODUCTION

Faith in some rescuer, in some type of god, in some type of custom, etc, which is all promulgation, and for me has no worth at all - that is not a strict life. Might we at any point happen from that point. Is it true or not that you are very certain we as a whole see that reality. A Catholic can be raised trusting in something - a deliverer, etc, as the greater part of the Christian folklore depends on that. That is, he's been adapted from adolescence, to accept - immersion, you know, its entire business. What's more, in India and different regions of the planet it is something very similar - from adolescence you are molded to trust in something, in god, in Atman, in Brahman, in a lifestyle, a strict life, with every one of its approvals and penances, with their ceremonies, doctrines, ministers, associations what not. Presently could we at any point really set to the Not become nonbelievers, not say, 'Indeed, that is all refuse, nothing exists', but rather we are attempting to inspect the entire issue of what religion is, what strict life is. Can we - assuming we are at all serious - could we at any point shove with or without that to the. Shoved regardless of that foggiest idea, it really depends on you. It

may not have a place with any faction or any gathering or any local area that has confidence in god, or doesn't put stock in god - that faith in god or no god, is one more type of dread. Correct. Mind needing a security, sureness of some sort, in light of the fact that our life is so unsure, so confounded, so futile, we believe that something should put stock in. So could we at any point additionally set that to the side. The expectation that something outside, a predominant organization exists - we will enquire, thusly all that must clearly be set to the side.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To Know The Influence of Educational Thought on Social Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti
2. To Know The Influence of Educational Thought on Religious Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the Influence of Educational Thought on Social Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti?
2. What is the Influence of Educational Thought on

Religious Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti ?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lutyens, Mary (2018), Every single day to day thought, sentiments, and exercises are on a superficial level, and beneath them is the psyche, the perspectives with which we are not comfortable, which put themselves out there sometimes through specific impersonations, instincts, and dreams. We are busy with one little corner of cognizance, which is a large portion of our life; the rest, that we call the inner mind, we don't have the foggiest idea how to get into. The psyche does exist and it is all around as inconsequential and dumb as the cognizant brain; as limited, as biased, restless, molded, and tacky.

McCoy, Ray (2017), As indicated by Krishnamurti, when one becomes mindful of one's molding, one figures out the whole awareness. Cognizance is the absolute field wherein contemplations, capabilities, and connections exist.

Aberbach, David (2016) , All thought processes, feelings, wants, delights, fears, goals, longings, trusts, distresses, delights, and motivations are in that field. Awareness can be separated into the dynamic and the torpid, the upper and lower levels.

Lutyens, Mary (2005), At the point when one knows about the entirety of awareness then one is working in complete focus, not halfway consideration. In such a state there is generally no rubbing. Grinding in life emerges when one attempts to separate one's awareness (Krishnamurti, 1983. We carry on with our life in parts. We are one individual working, one more with companions, and one more at home. A psyche that is divided won't ever know about full cognizance. One should reveal one's psyche, layer by layer, to grasp the sections individually. This is a cycle that might require weeks, months or even years (Krishnamurti, 1983.

RESEARCH GAP

Consideration isn't exactly the same thing as fixation. Fixation includes rejection, while consideration doesn't prohibit anything on Social & Religious Life . In the topic , *"Influence Of Educational Thought On Social & Religious Life By Jiddu Krishnamurti"* Typically we focus on our own concerns, our own thoughts, and our own reality, with the end goal that we are not equitably mindful. Verbally we must be shallow. What lies past can't be articulated. One should know. Mindfulness about how we walk, how we talk, how we talk, and our thought process, is important. It is with a choice less mindfulness that entryways will open and one would know a cognizance in which there is no contention and no time When change society and the world in which we track down ourselves. Understanding ourselves denotes the start of astuteness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, qualitative research methodology used by researchers for indication of complex landscape of jiddu krishnamurti and provides nuanced insights that quantitative methods alone may capture. this method remains invaluable in exploring the diversity of the

experience and social phenomena of jiddu krishnamurti.

Text analysis tools on jiddu krishnamurti go beyond traditional manual coding and allow for a more nuanced data analysis. the text algorithm sifts through the vast amount of textual feedback, identifying patterns, themes, and sentiment of social life and religious life by jiddu krishnamurti.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Then, at that point, likewise the brain should go past this longing to track down something, this chasing. Furthermore, that is considerably more troublesome - mentally one can see every one of the idiocies of religions, yet the psyche is looking for, not enquiring however looking for. It really want to believe that we see the distinction between the looking for and the enquiring. Looking for suggests (sound of plane) Looking for infers moving between different groups, one master to another, one faction to another, looking for in the event that you can track down bliss, happiness, fulfilment, in Buddhism, or in Harmony, or in Hinduism looking for. Furthermore, there are individuals who furnish what you need, individuals who discuss Buddhism, make sense of Buddhism, and you chasing, not knowing, being malcontent, despondent, hopeless, confounded, and trapped in that snare. Furthermore, you say, 'finally another faction or become a Socialist - 'Finally, there is the genuine stuff'.

As per objective 1st, To Know The Influence of Educational Thought on Social Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti,

So looking for additionally suggests acknowledgment, finding. What's more, looking for suggests acknowledgment in that which you have found. Isn't that so? And that implies, when you look for, you've definitely known, clearly. Also, subsequently it's not truth. So the brain should be liberated from each type of coordinated conviction, subsequently couldn't really have a place with any gathering, to any individual - it's anything but an individual faction. Also, we are worried about enquiry, thusly the entire inquiry of looking for, finding, is non-existent. The enquiry on the off chance that there is or there isn't a reality which isn't the result of thought. Correct, There's absolutely nothing that thought can't develop. There was a man once, It used to be aware, he tried different things with something which is very entertaining. He got a piece of stone which had a bizarre shape, and put it on the mantelpiece and consistently he proposed to that stone a blossom. Before the year's over he wouldn't be able to was lost with that bloom and that stone - that to him was reality. I couldn't say whether you follow this. Furthermore, he started for no reason in particular, and afterward he was gotten. So thought can develop, envision anything - divine beings, no divine beings, heavenly messengers, no heavenly messengers - follow - it can deliver each type of hypochondriac discernments, thoughts, ends. So knowing that insightfully, man says then, 'How could that believed be supposing that believed is fit - and it is - of anticipating, concocting,

envisioning, each type of end, a picture in which the human brain finds security, that security, that picture turns into a deception - the Friend in need, the Brahman, the Atman, the encounters you have through different types of disciplines.

All in all, the issue then is: can thought totally stay composed. What's more, they say you can make it still just through a framework. Correct? Satisfy we are examining, don't simply acknowledge whatever the speaker is saying. Since they all see the need of having the brain totally calm, since you can see when the psyche hushes up it can see significantly more, hear substantially more, see things as they are, not design, not envision. So might the psyche at any point be totally, totally stay composed. Furthermore, it must be stilled through, they say, discipline, control, through a specific type of a framework which their educator has created. Correct? You are following? Furthermore, could a framework, a discipline, a congruity at any point make the psyche calm, truly peaceful. Or then again following a framework, rehearsing many days, a large number of days, doesn't it make the psyche mechanical, and being mechanical then you have some control over it, similar to some other machine, you have some control over machines. Is it safe to say that you are following however, the cerebrum doesn't hush up, it has been molded, adapted by the framework which it has polished. In this manner such a cerebrum, being mechanical, it very well may be controlled and think such control is quietness, tranquillity.

As per objective 2nd, To Know The Influence of Educational Thought on Religious Life by Jiddu Krishnamurti

So might the psyche at any point be made Could the brain at any point turn out to be totally still without pressure, without impulse, without discipline being will, opposition, concealment, congruity, squeezing into an example pre-laid out. That's what assuming you do, you are constraining the psyche, through struggle, to adjust to the example laid out by the framework. You are following so discipline in the common feeling of as most people are already aware. Furthermore, the word 'discipline' signifies to learn, not to adjust, not to smother, not to control, but rather to learn. All in all, might the cerebrum and the psyche, the entire construction of the cerebrum and the brain at any point be totally calm with practically no type of mutilation by will, by want, by thought? So the issue lies with that. What's more, knowing it, individuals have said, 'That is impractical', thusly they headed down the other path - control, discipline, do a wide range of stunts, in Harmony - all that, they stay there, focusing, on that watching, , and assuming you nod off you are struck to keep alert. This sort of gigantic discipline, mechanical, and subsequently controllable, and through in the expectation of accomplishing an encounter which will be valid. Companions who have filled me in regarding it, genuine researchers - man as he continued looking for some really supernatural experience said, 'Brain should be totally tranquil to get something which it has never experienced,

which it has never tasted the smell, its nature'. In this manner he said, 'Psyche should stay composed.' And they've said there is just a single approach to making the brain still - compel it.

Anyway, what is the relationship of the obscure to the known. Knowledge has nothing at all to do with thought. You might be outrageously sharp, excellent at contention, exceptionally scholarly, have encountered, carried on with an enormous life, been from one side of the planet to the other, examining, looking, looking, gathered a lot of information, rehearsed Harmony, Hindu reflection, yet everything that has nothing at all to do with insight. Knowledge appears when the psyche, the heart and the body are truly agreeable.

Hence - follow this up - the body should be profoundly touchy, not gross, not, you know, eating, drinking and the remainder, you know, sex, you know all that makes the body coarse, dull, and weighty. Hence you need to see all that. The exceptionally seeing the reality of that causes you to eat less, makes the body gives the body its own knowledge, there is a consciousness of the body which isn't being constrained - the remainder of it. So the body turns out to be incredibly, delicate, you know, similar to a delightful instrument. The equivalent with the heart, which is, that it is rarely harmed and can never hurt another. That is innocence of the heart - not to hurt and not be harmed. Furthermore, the brain, having no trepidation, requesting no joy - not that you can't partake in the magnificence of life, excellence of the tree, excellence of a lovely face, taking a gander at kids, the progression of water, the mountains, the green fields - there is extraordinary savor the experience of that. However, that charm when sought after by thought becomes joy. So the brain must be, you know, void to obviously see.

So the connection between the tremendous the obscure and the known is this insight, which has nothing at all to do with Buddhism, with Harmony, with me or with you, with literally nothing to do with power or custom. Presently do you have that knowledge? That is the main point that is important. Then that knowledge will work in this world ethically. You get it? Profound quality then, at that point, is structure, which is righteousness - not the goodness or the ethical quality of society, which is absolutely unethical. So insight achieves request, which is prudence, and thusly a thing that is living, not mechanical. Isn't that so? In this way can never work on being great, you can never work on attempting to become unassuming. At the point when there is that knowledge, that insight normally achieves request, and the excellence of request.

Then mind is curious as to whether there is more than simple idea and its design. Man all through the ages has looked for this. He has enquired into the known and is continuously adding increasingly more into the field of the known - more information, more innovation, better method for correspondence, contamination, you realize all that is going on is inside the field of the known, including your divine beings, your deliverers, your lords, your masters, your edification - it's everything inside the field of

the realized which is the capability of thought. Correct.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- Might it be said that we are speaking with one another. So believed is estimation – correct in light of the fact that to gauge as per the known, as per the memory, as per information, experience. So they say, individuals say, 'You should contemplate to see whether there is something past the known'.
- Could it be said that you are following this , So they say, 'Control, control your idea, discipline your thought, become mindful of your idea,' so they are as yet managing naturally suspected - control by thought, discipline by thought. What's more, through thought they desire to find what isn't quantifiable. Isn't that so? And furthermore they say, you should quit thinking, kill the brain.
- We planned to talk toward the beginning of today about religion, contemplation, and to happen after something, on the off chance that it is conceivable, which isn't quantifiable, which is absolutely an alternate aspect. We discussed religion. Presently we will figure out meditating. It don't have any idea how it affects you. Assuming you had never heard that word, assuming you had never heard any of the masters letting you know how to think, it would be greatly improved, in light of the fact that then we would be able, the two of us together, explore it, not knowing.
- So it need to figure out how it affects a psyche that is fit for contemplation. The word reference importance of that word is 'to contemplate over, to be worried about, to have an educated person, a profound handle, etc. That is the word reference meaning.
- Also, there is the significance which every one of the religions has given to it, in various ways - examination, in the west, and contemplation in the east. Furthermore, being a human, It need to find out, in light of the fact that It don't have a place with the east or the west, I'm neither a Harmony devotee nor Krishnamurti supporter. It need to figure out meditating. However, It can see one thing obviously, that for however long believed is working, it should work as per the past and venture itself into the future - from the known to the known - It see that plainly. However long believed is in activity, the same old thing can happen.

CONCLUSION

It is notable that the ability to believe makes us not the same as other living creatures, however this tragically is likewise the motivation behind why we might view ourselves as higher in the request for nature. This extremely fundamental power is for the most part utilized and mishandled after some time. Our psyche is misjudged,

as per Krishnamurti, and we should begin utilizing it uniquely in contrast to it is utilized, and not as an article for self-security and self-extension. We are not any more crude people, and endurance impulses must be deserted in order to accomplish higher mindfulness. He discusses how, on the off chance that society needs to remain genuinely human, it should be in a condition of consistent unrest and re-assessment. The psyche is being involved something else for self image focused greed and for self-improvement and power, thusly reducing others open doors. We should attempt to have a place with a natural society and not a coordinated one; in light of the fact that a coordinated society will constantly follow a progressive system; and the guidelines of profound quality might exist, however not really in the nobler sense like that of a natural society . A natural society implies that its individuals must choose the option to have a place with it. In any case, it goes considerably further. It infers that they have no longing except for to have a place with it, for their inclinations and those of the general public are something similar; they distinguish themselves with the general public. Solidarity here isn't a rule declared by the specialists, however a reality acknowledged by every one of the members. No incredible penance is involved. One's place in the public eye might be burdensome or undignified, however it is the only one accessible; without it, one is not welcome on the planet. Something contrary to this point of view, with freedoms and freedoms allowed to an individual, shapes a coordinated society.

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